

A COMBINED MICRO- AND MACROMECHANICAL STUDY OF THE IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON AND GLASS FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The impact behaviour of four laminates is studied: glass-epoxy crossply and fabric, and two carbon epoxy crossplies with different matrix. The study tries to present a comprehensive data set: the impact event itself is fully documented, as load, velocity and deflection versus time curves as well as absorbed energy data are available. Damage is monitored quantitatively using computerised ultrasonic C-scan. Compression after impact tests have been carried out to assess the residual mechanical properties. The results are qualitatively related to the mechanical properties of the laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates, used in light weight structures, are often thin plates. They are extremely stiff and strong, and quite damage tolerant when loaded in plane; however, when loaded perpendicular to the laminate plane, damage tolerance is very sensitive to the interlaminar properties of the composite. Impact loads are a typical example of this class of loading. During a non-penetrating impact, damage can initiate as matrix cracks, and grow into delaminations. At very high energy impacts, also fibre fracture can occur; eventually, the laminate will be penetrated by the impactor.

It is clear that many studies have been devoted to the impact problem in composites. A large amount of experimental data have been generated, for all kinds of laminates, under many different experimental conditions. Even if we limit ourselves to the materials science aspects of the problem (deliberately omitting the dynamical behaviour of composite structures under impact loading), two major questions remain unanswered:

- a. which material parameters do control the damage initiation and development during impact loading
- b. how is the residual strength of an impacted laminate related to the impact damage.

One could try to answer these questions by developing a first model which can predict impact damage, and a second one which can relate damage to residual mechanical properties. Preparing the development of such a model, we however found out that there are almost no comprehensive, systematically generated and complete data available in literature. So, if we would like to check the validity of available or newly created models, we need to construct our own, complete set of data. This data set should

at least contain the following information:

- a. an accurate description of the impact event itself: load, velocity and deflection versus time, absorbed energy;
- b. a careful, quantitative assessment of impact damage
- c. reliable and relevant data on residual mechanical properties.

Checking the validity of models furthermore requires a well controlled and balanced selection of laminates, on which the aforementioned experiments will be carried out.

In this report, the results of a small part of our systematic experimental study on the impact performance of composite laminates will be discussed. Results on four materials will be presented: glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy, both in crossply and in fabric form. Later, in a future publication, results on aramid-epoxy, and on the influence of testing parameters will be reported as well.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL

Three materials contain the same epoxy matrix (Ciba Geigy 913, failure strain= 3 %, cure temperature = 120°C). The second carbon-epoxy contains a different epoxy resin (Ciba Geigy 920, failure strain= 7 %, cure temperature = 125°C). Two fibre types are used: the normal E-glass fibres, or T300-carbon fibres. In the prepregs, these fibres can be present in two forms: either unidirectional, or as fabrics; in the latter case, a plain weave fabric was used. The prepreg fibre volume fraction in both systems was slightly different ($V_f = 70\%$ for the glass-UD and 58 % for the carbon-UD against 62% for the glass-fabric). The laminate lay up was $(O,90)_4s$ for the UD-prepregs (16 layers), and 8 layers for the fabric prepregs; both layups resulted in a laminate thickness of about 2 mm.

In all the figures, the four materials will be represented by the following symbols:

	symbol	line
glass- UD	□	—————
glass fabric	+	-----
carbon-UD-913	◇	—————
carbon-UD-920	△	-----

IMPACT TESTING

A home built Instrumented Falling Weight Impact Tester (IFWIT) has been used; this apparatus has been described in detail elsewhere { 2 }. The plates are clamped in between two steel plates with a square opening of 80x80 mm. From the load-versus-time curve, velocity, deflection and energy are calculated by simple and double integration. The total (or maximum) and absorbed energy are normalized over the thickness; hence the unit is J/mm.

DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

A home built, computerised ultrasonic C-scan apparatus (based on Krautkrämers USIP-12) is used to detect and measure the delaminated area. Moreover, the quality of each plate is controlled by C-scan before impact testing. Damage is further assessed by optical microscopy studies of polished cross sections, intersecting the impact point.

RESIDUAL PROPERTIES

In this report, only results on compression tests will be reported. Compression strength is measured using an ITTRI-type fixture. Specimen width is 50 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ABSORBED ENERGY

At low total impact energy, carbon-epoxy composites absorb more energy than glass-epoxy ones (fig.1). However, at about 5 J/mm, serious fibre fracture is initiated. The glass-epoxy laminates can withstand much more impact energy; up to 10J/mm, the energy absorption is higher for the fabric than for the crossply composites.

The reasons for these differences are numerous, and will, in the limited scope of this paper, only be discussed qualitatively. It is first important to realize that an impact test is an **energy controlled** event! This means that the reaction of the laminate on the imposed energy will depend on the deformation behaviour, and hence on the mechanical properties of the material. The available impact energy (also called total or maximum energy) can conceptually be split up in two parts:

$$E_{tot} = E_{el} + E_{inel}$$

The elastic part is given back to the impactor, the inelastic part is in itself further distributed over several physical events: vibration and damping of the plate, heat and sound, and damage:

$$E_{tot} = E_{el} + E_{vib} + E_{hs} + E_{dam}$$

For the further analysis, it will be assumed, as a first approximation, that the total energy is only distributed over **elastic** deformation and **damage** initiation and development.

If this simplification is accepted, it is clear that the elastic part will be larger for glass-epoxy laminates: although the modulus is lower, the strain to failure for glass fibres is much higher than for carbon fibres (T300), so that serious damage due to fibre failure is delayed. A further explanation can be formulated when we look at the damage area.

DAMAGE AREA

As a function of the total impact energy, carbon-epoxy composites show a rapidly, and linearly, increasing damage area (fig.2). The damage area in glass-epoxy composites seems to level off at 5 J/mm, but increases again from 10 J/mm on. However, as a function of the **absorbed** energy, the damage area increases **linearly** (fig.3). Several conclusions can be drawn from these data.

First, they indicate that the energy dissipated in damage, is mainly used to create delaminations. Although the "damage area" mentioned here is a projection on the plane of the laminate of all delaminations inbetween different plies (as ultrasonic C-scan was used to detect them), fig.3 clearly indicates that the energy to grow a delamination is the highest for the glass-fabric composite, lower for the glass-crossply and the lowest for the carbon-epoxy composites. - *In fact, the energy per delamination area is inversely proportional with the slope of the curves in fig.3* - These findings are in agreement with the differences in interlaminar fracture toughness: it is about 800 J/m² for glass-epoxy, about 300 J/m² for carbon-epoxy. Even the difference in toughness of the 913 and the 920 epoxy resin can be traced back: the tougher one (920) shows a smaller damage area.

Second, the leveling off in the glass-epoxy curves (fig.2) indicates that two different damage mechanisms are present. Most probably, the delamination initiation (first slope) is followed by widespread debonding of the glass fibres (lower interface strength, higher stress concentration around the glass than around the carbon fibres), which inhibites further delamination growth. Moreover, the onset of further delamination growth is delayed because of the high interlaminar fracture toughness of glass-epoxy composites.

Third, the extremely small delamination area in glass-fabric composites not only proves that the interlaminar fracture toughness is high, but also that the nature itself of the fabric introduces additional damage (at the cross-over points of the rovings), which consumes additional energy.

RESIDUAL MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The results of the compression-after-impact (CAI) tests are shown in fig. 4 (absolute values) and fig.5 (related to the compression strength before impact). It is obvious that, in both representations, glass-epoxy composites perform better than carbon-epoxy. In both groups, a further difference can be observed: on one hand, the carbon epoxy with the tougher resin has a higher CAI value, on the other hand, the glass fabric performs better in relative terms than the glass-crossply.

To explain these differences, we first can plot the CAI versus the absorbed energy: the differences are even larger (fig.6). If however we plot the compression-after-impact strength versus the damage area (fig.7), only two lines remain: one for the glass-epoxy, another for the carbon-epoxy. This means that the damage area uniquely controls the CAI-strength; the reason for this being that failure during a compression test on an impact laminate is controlled by the local buckling of the delaminated plies: the larger the delamination, the easier buckling can occur. The lower values for the carbon-epoxy reflect the lower interlaminar fracture toughness of these materials, as the failure due to buckling is preceded by further growth of the delaminations.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a comprehensive set of data on impact behaviour of carbon-epoxy crossply and glass-epoxy crossply and fabric composites has been presented. It has been shown that the energy, absorbed during impact, is mainly consumed by delamination growth. A qualitative explanation for the differences between glass and carbon composites has been presented, based on the inplane and interlaminar mechanical properties of the laminates. It was finally shown that the compression after impact strength is related to the damage area, because CAI is a buckling controlled phenomenon.

In a future publication, a model will be presented which will support the qualitative explanations with quantitative relations.

fig.1: absorbed energy versus total energy

fig.2: damage area versus total energy

fig.3: damage area versus absorbed energy

fig.4: compression-after-impact strength versus total energy

fig.5: compression-after-impact strength (related to the initial compr. strength) versus total energy

fig.6: compression-after-impact strength (related to the initial compr. strength) versus absorbed energy

fig.7: compression-after-impact strength (related to the initial compression strength) versus damage area